

Kinetics of Methoxymercuration of Olefins.

Part-I : Substituted Cinnamic Acids*

K. K. Satpathy, Ashok K. Patnaik, P. L. Nayak and M. K. Rout†

A value of -1.57 ± 0.1 has been obtained for the Hammett reaction constant ' ρ ' for the methoxymercuration of substituted cinnamic acids at 40° . The value of the isokinetic temperature β was found to be 720°K and a linear relationship was found to exist between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$. A probable mechanism has been suggested

The addition of oxy salts of mercury to olefins (oxymercuration) to give β -oxyorgano-mercury (II) derivatives is a well known reaction.¹⁻⁴ While the stoichiometry and stereochemistry of the reaction have been extensively investigated^{2,4} there are virtually no reliable data concerning its kinetics with regard to the applicability of Hammett equation⁵ to these types of reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The substituted Cinnamic acids were prepared and purified by the method described by Vogel.⁶ The mercuric acetate used was of 'AnalaR' grade. The method of rate measurement was that described by Das and Mallick⁷.

DISCUSSION

Leffler⁸ has shown that $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ can be linearly related by the equation

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

So that

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger - (T - \beta) \Delta S^\ddagger$$

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† Principal, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3.

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Then if ' β ', termed the isokinetic temperature, is within the experimentally accessible temperature range, ' ρ ' can change sign with consequent ambiguity in interpretation in terms of reaction mechanism.

A linear relationship between the enthalpy of activation and the entropy of activation has been found for the oxy-mercuration of substituted cinnamic acids. From the above relationship, $\Delta H_0^\ddagger$ was found to be 26.3K. cals per mole and ' β ' the iso-kinetic temperature was found to be 463°K. At this temperature all the reactions have the same rate coefficient if the relationship were perfectly obeyed. The temperature is not within the range of present investigation and has practically no importance.

It has been shown by Exner⁹ that ' β ' can also be calculated from the slope λ of the plot of $\log k$ at T_1 against $\log k$ at T_2 , where k is the specific rate, using the relationship

$$\beta = T_2 \frac{T_1 \lambda - T_1}{T_1 \lambda - T_2}$$

From our results $\lambda = 0.99$, so that $\beta = 720^\circ\text{K}$. Since $T_2/T_1 = 0.98$, these results put the reaction in the most common category (Exner's category⁹ 3a). It can be concluded, therefore that the oxy-mercuration of substituted cinnamic acids is normal and a linear relationship exists between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ as given below :

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + 720 \Delta S^\ddagger$$

A regression line was fitted to $\log k$ values against the Hammett ' σ ' values for para- and meta-substituted cinnamic acids. The value of ' ρ ', the reaction constant was found to be -1.57 ± 0.1 .

Bearing in mind the observation of Leffler⁸ and Exner⁹ it is useful to examine the values of $\Delta F^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ with the σ values. The values of $\Delta F^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger$ are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Name of the substituents in Cinnamic acid	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ k. cals/ mole 308°K	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ k. cals/ mole 313°K	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ k. cals/ mole	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cals/ deg./ mole
<i>o</i> -OMe	11.630	11.808	10.133	-34.61
<i>p</i> -OMe	12.305	12.454	11.515	-30.31
<i>p</i> -Me	12.034	12.241	11.976	-31.73
<i>p</i> -ipr.	12.644	12.782	13.357	-28.09
<i>m</i> -OMe	13.143	13.265	14.739	-24.94
H	13.081	13.787	15.684	-22.42

In drawing conclusions concerning the mechanism of the reaction, it is tacitly assumed that the variation of free energy with substituent $\left(\frac{\partial \Delta F^\ddagger}{\partial \sigma} \right)$, where σ is the Hammett substituent constant) is approximately independent of temperature as calculated below :

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial \Delta F^\ddagger}{\partial \sigma} \right]_{313} &= 6.25 \text{ K.cals.} \\ \left[\frac{\partial \Delta F^\ddagger}{\partial \sigma} \right]_{308} &= 6.36 \text{ K.cals.} \\ \left[\frac{\partial \Delta H^\ddagger}{\partial \sigma} \right]_{313} &= 15 \text{ K.cals.} \\ \left[\frac{\partial \Delta S^\ddagger}{\partial \sigma} \right]_{313} &= 2.77 \text{ cal/degree} \end{aligned}$$

Thus it may be assumed that the entropy of activation is independent of temperature¹⁰. In these circumstances $\rho_1/\rho_2 = T_2/T_1$ so that the variation of ρ with temperature is small¹¹.

Mechanism of the reaction : Two mechanisms, one ionic and the other non-ionic have been proposed for the addition of mercuric salts to olefins^{2,3}. Wright and co-workers¹² have concluded that ionic mechanism can occur only for those alkenes in which σ bond participation is possible as in a bicyclic alkenes like norbornene. Similar participation may also be possible for olefinic compounds and hence the reaction may proceed through an ionic mechanism, possibly by way of an "alkene-mercurinium" ion as suggested below :—

Step (1) is here the rate determining step and the reaction is clearly first order with respect to each reactant, as observed. In step (2) which is considerably faster than step (1) the solvent molecules (methanol) attack the "alkene mercurinium-ion" with a result of trans

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opening of the latter and the formation of the methoxy mercuric acetate salt of the olefinic compound (cinnamic acid) used.

The reactive species I is probably a π -complex and may well contain a three membered ring which is rigid enough to make possible the maintenance of the configuration.

The $>C=O$ group conjugated to the ethylenic system deactivates the $>C=C<$ bond towards electrophilic reagents and as expected for an electrophilic addition, the rate of oxy-mercuration is increased by electron donating substituents and retarded by electron-withdrawing substituent (vide Table II).

TABLE II

Values of specific reaction rate at 40° for the methoxy-mercuration of substituted cinnamic acids.

Substituent	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -iPr
$k \times 10^3$ mole ⁻¹ Sec ⁻¹	51.16	48.40	11.25	7.67
Substituent	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	
$k \times 10^3$ l mole ⁻¹ Sec ⁻¹	4.15	3.33	2.12	

The plot of $\log k$ vs. σ values yields the value of $\rho = -1.57 \pm 0.1$, implying a high degree of positive charge delocalisation (approaching a non-classical carbonium ion character) in the transition state as shown below.

A similar correlation between $\log k$ and σ ($\rho = -1.77$) has been reported by Kreevoy *et al*¹⁴ for the deoxymercuration of a series of oxymereurials. On the basis of analogous observations concerning the effect of substituents on the rate of the oxidation of olefins by thallium (III), for which a mechanism involving a rate-determining oxythallium step was proposed, Henry¹⁵ has reached similar conclusions favouring a transition state with considerable carbonium ion character. On the other hand, a completely free (open) carbonium ion intermediate in oxymercuration appears to be ruled out by the failure to observe cis-trans isomerisation during the successive oxy-mercuration, -deoxymercuration of olefins such as cis- or trans butene or cis-stilbene^{16,17}.

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Mayurbhanj Chemical Laboratory,
Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-3.

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